

DEVELOPING THE METHODOLOGY OF SPEECH CULTURE DEVELOPMENT OF FUTURE EDUCATORS- PSYCHOLOGISTS

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Abstract. *In this article, the development of the speech culture of future pedagogues-psychologists and improvement of the methodology is considered. In addition, it was also analyzed that teachers' speech culture education is related to all subjects and serves to enrich the student's personality in harmony with the educational process.*

Keywords: *pedagogue-psychologist, speech culture, personality, method, society, state.*

Person, his or her all-round harmonious development, well-being, creation of conditions and effective mechanisms for realization of personal interests, change of outdated patterns of thinking and social behavior are the main goal and driving force of the reforms implemented in the republic. The formation of an excellent system of personnel training based on the rich intellectual heritage of the people and universal values, on the basis of the achievements of modern culture, economy, science and technology, is an important condition for the development of Uzbekistan. National personnel training program The program prepared in accordance with the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" aims to implement the national model of personnel training, comprehensively matured, adapted to life in society, educational and professional program It implies the creation of social-political, legal, psychological-pedagogical and other conditions for conscious selection and subsequent thorough mastering, and education of citizens who feel their responsibility before society, state and family. Therefore, the development of speech culture of future pedagogues-psychologists cannot fail to be of great importance.

Speaking of speech culture, the culture of speech means that there are a number of communicative qualities such as correctness, accuracy, logicity, expressiveness, richness, purity, smoothness that affect the power of the sphere of influence. A speech that embodies all these qualities is considered cultural. The main issue in speech culture is the appropriate use of language. Therefore, the analysis of real social processes of language use is one of the important areas of this field. The teacher's speech should be an example for the student in following the standards of literary pronunciation. Violation of the norms of literary pronunciation occurs primarily as a result of dialect. Therefore, it is not easy for the teacher to completely free his and his students' speech from the dialectal articulatory base and phonetic laws of the dialect.

Speech culture is an important sign of the cultural and educational development of the society and the spiritual maturity of the nation. It is an important sign of cultural maturity in the literal sense. Cultural speech in the real sense is one of the important aspects of the general cultural level of a person. That is why spiritual and educational reforms in our country are now more urgent than ever.

In the laws of our republic "On State Language", "On Education", "National Program on Personnel Training" and many other documents, spiritual and educational education and language issues are of special importance is given. Every member of our society, every specialist should keep pace with the times, and first of all, be a loyal master of his native language.

Language grows together with society, its spirituality, enlightenment and culture [1].

In the vernacular, there are special speech tools for both greetings and farewells. The teacher is an example for everyone and for his students to use them properly. A cultured person should be able to admit his guilt and know how to ask for forgiveness for his guilt. Apologizing for one's fault is not a blow to one's pride, but a sign of decency and politeness. Another characteristic of a mature person is good manners. In our language, there are impressive phrases used when saying goodbye, such as "goodbye, be healthy", "goodbye, see you", "goodbye, let's see you in peace". It is appropriate if the teacher uses the expressions "goodbye, be healthy" and "goodbye, stay well" when leaving the classroom.

It is also necessary to teach the child the manners of expressing gratitude on time to those who have done good, done the requested work, and fulfilled the request. There are beautiful expressions in our language that mean encouragement and gratitude. Bringing them into everyday life, using them in their place, decorates a person's behavior. The teacher should encourage students who have completed the task well with words such as "well done", "good luck", "thank you", "thank you father", "thank you".

"Each person's level of culture and education can be determined by his written and spoken speech" (S. Ibrohimov) [2].

Mutual relations of pedagogue-psychological personnel are built on the basis of pedagogy of cooperation, democracy, respect, recognition of self-worth. This, of course, serves to improve speech culture. If uncertainty is felt in the teacher's speech, it will have a negative effect on the student's personality. In particular, the student becomes shy, aloof and careless in communication with his peers. In addition, such a child's interest in learning the surroundings decreases, which later causes the inability to learn lessons in educational institutions.

The role of pedagogues and parents in education of speech communication in school-aged children is huge. In the process of working on children's speech:

- to be polite in conversation with peers;
- to speak in a natural tone;
- to look at the face of the soulmate when speaking;
- it is necessary to pay attention to keeping his hands in a relaxed position. We know that there is an integral connection between science and thought, they cannot live without each other.

In this regard, at the beginning of the last century, the great Uzbek linguist and writer Abdurauf Fitrat, in his article entitled "Our Language", complained about the tendency of Uzbek intellectuals to use Persian and Arabic words and wrote: "*Dunyoning eng boy, eng baxtsiz bir tili qaysi tildir? Bilasizmi? Turkcha (o'zbekcha)!. Ming yildan beri ezila kelmishdir. Lekin bitmamishdir. Bitmas, yashamishdir, yashar. Negakim boydir. Turkcha yashamishdir. Yashar, lekin o'zini arab, fors tillarindan qutqara olurmi, yo'g'mi? So'zni bu yerga yetirgach, barmog'imni yaraning o'zagiga bosmish bo'ldim*" [3]

The teacher's speech should be an example for the student in following the standards of literary pronunciation. Violation of the norms of literary pronunciation occurs, first of all, as a result of the influence of dialect. Therefore, the teacher should always remember to protect his and his students' speech from the influence of dialectal pronunciation. It is not easy to completely get

rid of the articulatory base of the dialect and the phonetic laws of the dialect formed from childhood [4].

Improving speech culture, successful speech requires the teacher to develop a number of special abilities: social-perceptive ability, social imagination ability, self-control ability, ability to control one's mental state in communication, willful influence, the ability to show, convince. The development of general mental and physical characteristics of a person, which creates conditions for the successful acquisition of speech skills and abilities, includes the development of imagination, figurative memory and fantasy.

Correctness of speech is its central quality, but speech culture it is impossible to provide this quality alone. Undoubtedly, every no true speech is clear or smooth, pure or rich, in general, cannot be worthy of sufficient influence power. That's why speech a number of linguists engaged in researching the problems of culture that it is expedient to distinguish two stages of speech culture they emphasize. For example, L.I. Skvortsov the general concept of "speech culture" representing the two stages of acquisition and use of literary language that it should be divided into two parts in the form of "correctness of speech" and "speech culture" emphasizing, he gives them the following explanation: "The first, lower stage of speech is the correctness. We are talking about correctness in literary discourse and mastering its standards we will talk in the process. Evaluation of options about the correctness of speech: correct - incorrect, a Russian expression is not a Russian expression, etc. The correctness of speech is essentially is a subject of school education. The high school curriculum is generally correct speech (more in the field of grammar) aims to build competence [4]

As a result of our research, we can say that the speech of a pedagogue-psychologist at the required level is the most important integral part of the general speech culture. Live sound speech and the correct eventing of all its elements means the total speech technique of skills and competences. A teacher who is devoted to his profession appears in the eyes of his students as a flawless and knowledgeable, valuable teacher. It is desirable for a teacher to always work on himself, to be aware of the news, to look positively at innovations, and to be an eloquent person himself.

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